

Mapping conocimiento and desconocimiento in collaborative mathematics teacher professional development

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Using Case Study, this paper demonstrates the ways a group of teachers in Chile experienced collaborative knowing as they participated in Lesson Study for professional development. I use Anzaldúa's conception of Conocimiento, reimagined for math teacher learning by Gutiérrez, to analyse data and understand the ways this team of teachers co-created knowledge together. Data includes transcribed audio/video recordings of planning meetings, lessons, and post-lesson reflections as well as participant interviews and focus groups. This study contributes to the discussion on mathematics teacher professional development including the preparation of teachers for advocating for their students within systems of oppression.

Lesson Study in Chile

Lesson Study incorporates teachers working together to plan a lesson, enact and learn from that lesson and then participate in collective reflection on student learning observed in that lesson (Fernandez & Yoshida, 2004). It is a system of teacher learning that was developed in a grassroots way for over one-hundred years in Japan and prioritizes teachers' perspectives in their learning. Lesson Study can be done alone as its key feature is reflection on one's practice through attention on student learning. Collaboration with other teachers, coaches and administrators provides additional lenses for that reflection (Fernandez et al., 2003). Juxtaposed to more popular models where millions of dollars are spent on professional development, where many studies have shown that professional development for teachers is fragmented and superficial, largely ignoring what research has demonstrated about teacher learning (Ball & Cohen, 1999; Borko, 2004; Putnam & Borko, 1997). Gellert et al. (2013) found that with elementary math teachers in Chile nationwide professional development efforts had the opposite effect of what was intended. Due to Chile's neoliberal past, living in the shadow of the Pinochet dictatorship that produced the high-risk teacher evaluations coupled with job insecurity, researchers have found teachers will teach 'safe' lessons that refrain from activities that might demonstrate errors or misconceptions (Araya & Dartnell, 2008). It is likely these same precautions are demonstrated in Lesson Study.

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Methodology

This research sought to answer the following questions: *What cycles of Conocimiento do teachers of Mathematics experience while engaged in Lesson Study in Chile? and What do we as math teacher educators and math teacher education researchers learn about teacher learning by focusing on uncertainties as they arise when the group is trying to construct new knowledge?* Coming from a social constructivist perspective and using Anzaldúa’s framework of Nepantla/Conocimiento and Gutiérrez’s reimagining of Nepantla for mathematics teacher learning in the Path of Conocimiento, I used Case Study with an ethnographic, qualitative approach to explore teacher learning through several cycles of Lesson Study as they were enacted over the course of one year. Data included analytic memos, audio and video transcribed recordings of collaborative lesson planning, lesson implementation, and collaborative lesson reflections. Data also includes teacher personal reflections, artifacts from the lessons and lesson planning. Lastly, teacher interviews and member checking sessions were also recorded and analyzed. Data was analyzed based on themes from the Path of Conocimiento as well as using inductive analysis. Nepantla was used to represent tensions or liminal spaces observed in the data. This is later represented by a 20-pointed star. When participants rejected interpretations in ways that shut down the exploration, they were coded as Desconocimiento. If comments or actions built on interpretations, clarified, or posited additional interpretations which respected both speakers, they were coded as Conocimiento, knowing. This longitudinal, situated Case Study design employed holistic single-case design outlined by Yin, (2018).

Figure 1: The Path of Conocimiento from Gutiérrez (2012)

Teacher	Grade/Subject	Experience (yrs.)	Yrs. at School	Gender
Valentina	Instructional Coach	30	30	F
Emilio	5 th to 8 th Grade Math	11	1	M
Violeta	2 nd Grade	7	1	F
Martina	3 rd Grade	6	0.5	F
Paloma	Classroom Aid	13	13	F
Elena	1 st Grade	2	1	F

Table 1: Teacher/ Administrative Participants.

Context

This paper looks at a specific instance of conocimiento that emerged in the second of three cycles of Lesson Study carried out in one school. The objective of the lesson was to build understanding of the concept of tens and ones among a class of 1st grade students. As a secondary goal, the team sought to explore student collaboration through teacher-lead learning centers. The head teacher for the class, Elena, designed four centers which were introduced at the beginning of the class. Students were then sent to one of the four centers and then rotated as the teacher instructed. Video cameras were positioned around the room to capture the work in the classroom as a whole as well as at each of the centers. These videos then were edited to follow three focal students as they moved from center to center, so that the teachers could collaboratively reflect on one small set of students as the progressed through the centers. In the reflection meeting, teachers were given reflection sheets to record thoughts independently before they watched the edited video of the focal students.

Data analysis

After the lesson, students were dismissed to the school patio where they enjoyed a recess with the other classes. As we walked out of the classroom Martina and Violeta said that they felt the lesson had “gone well” and enjoyed “working together in the same room” but did not mention the lesson or their observations made in the lesson. Later, in Emilio’s home, he began to process the events at his center. He explained that his student did not know her numbers yet, “She confused the ten and the one.” He explained that generally the students performed poorly in his school and he cited poverty factors for why the school scores were so low on the state exams.

And why do you see this? Why does this happen? It’s because the parents have low income. I’ve checked those statistics and the parents sometimes have an eighth grade [education]... (Interview, June 28) ^A

Emilio’s referencing poverty as an explanation of student performance was the beginning of the representations from the teaching group indicating that there were problems in

student performance. The second indication was found in the common language in the reflection, predominantly speaking about student engagement in general but positive terms. Specifically, teacher referred to the students as “happy” and “motivated” or “happy and “excited to participate” (see Table 2.) Only three “suggestions” were given in all reflections. Two where on Emilio’s reflection page, meaning that most did not offer suggestions.

Observations	Suggestions
<p>Alumnos contentos experimentos y ansiosos por participar. Se comunican para desarrollar la actividad</p>	<p>Falta plantear objetivos a los alumnos. (cont.) actividad de cierre. * Leng Matemáticas Actividad inicial (motivación)</p>
<p>Alumnos contentos y motivados en las actividades, lo que genero una buena adquisición del contenido.</p>	<p>QUIZAS PUDO MEJORAR LA EXPOSICIÓN YA QUE LA LECCIÓN FUE COROTA en todo momento. en todo momento.</p>
<p>Estaban contentos y se comunicaron porque se les comentaban. Si siempre</p>	<p>QUIZAS SE PUDO Aprovechar la instancia PARA profundizar los contenidos.</p>

Table 2: Sample Comments from Teacher Reflection.

Despite predominantly positive comments from the independent reflections, there was a perceivable difference in mood among the teachers in the reflection compared to the planning meeting and the lesson. Where our planning time at the beginning of the week was energetic and full of ideas, the reflection was more reserved. One way to see this was in the coding: as the teachers were eager to share, they began to speak over one another, making transcribing difficult. These moments were coded as cross-speak. There were 3 cross-speak moments in this reflection.

Planning Meeting 1	Reflection 1	Planning Meeting 2	Reflection 2	Impromptu Reflection (3)	Reflection 3	Totals
24	0	9	3	12	2	50

Table 3: Cross-speech across lesson study meetings. Note that the first and second reflections had 2 and 4 participants, respectively.

We watched Emilio’s center, as the focus student counted with tiles, “17, 18, 19, 30.” To remediate, Emilio tried to get the student to count her tens and then to count on from the tens. He repeated the activity with different sets of tiles. When she answered correctly, she did so with an inflection at the end, indicating that she was not sure of her answer.

As the video played, it became evident that the teacher of the class, Elena, was uncomfortable. She shrunk down in her seat and kept her hands folded in front of her, partially obscuring her face, see Figures 2. (Note that the figures include a timestamp, this is only to communicate the passage of time.) As other teachers began mirroring her stance (see the third image in Figure 2), I was alerted to a tension happening in the group. As the video played, the mentor, Valentina quietly asked Elena (not the group) if the student knew the material. Elena responded, “Yes, she was just very nervous because of all the people and the cameras...”^B

Figure 2: Teacher Tension

After watching one center, I paused the video and asked if the student had learned the objective (23:45.81). The teachers all said “yes”.^C These were the three moments leading up to this conversation that demonstrated the teachers were experiencing some conflict with what was observed in the lesson. A: Emilio explained that the student was mixing her tens and ones and then cited poverty. B: When asked whether the student knew the material, Elena said yes but that the situation in the room had made her nervous. C: When asked if the student had learned, everyone said yes, and then said nothing. These pre-indicators are representing by triangles in Figure 3.

2 (24:01:09) Valentina: This is a concept we teach through many grades. We have been working on it since kindergarten.

Comments A, B, C and 2 demonstrated that the teachers might have been expecting a fault to land, that I or others were looking for a person or factors that were to take the blame. This progression is represented in a straight path, opposed to the turn represented in *conocimiento*. In the straight path, we see *desconocimiento*, we see missed opportunities. The *desconocimiento* presents a refusal to see students learning as a place to hone practice, but as simply as a factor in grading teachers in summative ways. With new perspective/interpretations, with challenges, we see the opportunity to begin making new knowledge collectively. A *conocimiento* move from 1 to 2 could have been *yes, and*: “Yes I noticed that she was using the numbers interchangeable, but I think it relates to her confusion of ones and tens.” or “yes, but I wonder if it is a language thing... not a number thing?”. Instead comment 2 re-centers the conversation and reiterates that this is something learned over time and that there is nothing to discuss concerning what was observed.

Figure 3: Building *Conocimiento*, A conversation diagram and a shift in body-language, observing Emilio (3) and agreeing (4).

3 (24:09:25) Emilio: I thought they understood that a ten was ten ones.... *maybe it was me. I think when I counted backward, going down and down and down, it confused her.* Also, all the people and the cameras could have made her nervous.

- 4 (25:07.31) Elena: Yes, because in fact, in class the kids do well. *But they struggle with complexity.* We committed a lot of time to it because it was hard for them to understand. They could understand that in tens there were 10 units representing 10 disks. Then for one group of tens they had a hard time because they had already said there were 18... for example, there are 18 already, but we have only one ten, 'How many were ones?' [the children would respond] 'One!' What? No, a group of 10!

Emilio presented himself as possibly making an error, an attention to discuss. Elena uses this moment to discuss an observation in the class, the confusion with the ten and the one. In this, she introduces an obstacle to understanding tens and ones well-documented in research (Fuson et al., 1997; Guerrero et al., 2020; Kevin Miller et al., 2000).

- 5 (25:53.11) Emilio: ...talking with another colleague... She did an activity where they gathered 10 balls of dough. *And those 10 balls of playdough, she combined... then perhaps the children will not be confused with a ones and the tens...* that they are not the same, because ten is bigger. Maybe that's what happened to the children with this activity. Because they confused one with a ten, when they are bigger... perhaps does not make sense, because it is obviously the ten largest. But for them as they were confused there.
- 6 (26:33.80) Elena: But first they were shown the loose quantity. There are 10 chips. Then I joined them and said, 'Look at these tens and there are ten. And this one, each of these pieces is called unit.' So, I show the units and they gather ten units...

Here Elena answers Emilio's suggestion with examples of what she did in class, and what she did at her center. Here we see Elena challenging Emilio's suggestion.

- 7 (27:06.61) Author: But maybe it was the way it was written? because it looks very similar... *Because normally we write 18 like this...* They might be guessing what we want.

Figure 4: Artifacts from the reflection, My depiction in my notes and screen capture of cards at the observed center.

- 8 (27:19.83) Emilio: Maybe they did not understand the instructions.
9 (27:25.34) Valentina: Maybe it is the other way around...
10 (28:14.05) Author: Judging by her facial expressions and how she was mixing 20 and 30... [cross speak] ... I wonder if she was not hearing the difference between the sounds.

This marks our first cross-speech. We had entered the problem-solving stage; we had been building and considering each other's ideas/interpretations since Emilio presented that maybe he had confused her. Here we see increase excitement and engagement. We then received important information from the classroom aid, who had worked with the student across grades.

- 11 (28:43.93) Elena: In fact, with her, you have to enunciate your words
12 (28:45.73) Paloma: She *watches the mouth a lot*. [cross speak] I had her in prekindergarten. If she did not see your mouth, she did not understand.
13 (29:06.90) Emilio: Was she evaluated?
14 (29:12.69) Paloma: In kindergarten, she had hearing aids... These tests are done periodically; the mom controls that. [Cross talk] The mom says that it got better and then fell.
15 (29:24.46) Violeta: ... she must have gone many years without being diagnosed then *she learned to listen to people by the movement of their mouth*. Then it takes a few years with hearing aids... A year and a half? It is just processing the movement of the mouth with the sound coming out. *I also think the concept is difficult*.

Here we see the combination of observation culminating in identifying what will be specifically difficult for this student. In the post-reflection interview, it was revealed that one obstacle to a productive collaborative reflection was that criticizing felt like betrayal.

It is my personal desire to support and not to betray my colleague, accusing her, accusing her that her work is not well done... It was Elena's class, her student. Elena said the student knew, but she was nervous... Then I also think that she was justifying herself... to not look bad, because that was her student. (Emilio, post-reflection interview)

Emilio's ability to have empathy for his colleagues while choosing to engage in difficult conversations helped to provide the brave space the group needed to learn from their practice. He could have simply agreed that the student was nervous in the reflection meeting, and the learning would have stopped there. Alternatively, he could have simply stated what he had told me, "The student doesn't know how to count." It would provide a missed opportunity to learn and to engage in professional development as the silence would likely have continued. It is clear for him, the tension included his interpretation, the care of his colleagues and their collaborative relationships and the interpretations being given from the group. Emilio prioritized the solidarity of the group to navigate the tension within the perspectives because he felt that an environment of solidarity is key to developing a productive learning space.

As a part of the member checking process, in zoom meetings with the teachers involved in this lesson and reflection, I showed the teachers the clip of this phenomena and asked them to remember what they were thinking. In the follow-up interview, Emilio stated, "I am a normal teacher and we all make mistakes. So, *I give the foot* or give the opportunity... I speak honestly and I think it drives others to see that we are all equal and they can tell their real experience without putting on a show." By modeling with self-criticism, he made space to engage with the differing perspectives in way that was candid and productive.

Discussion

Using this mapping tool, I was able to document how the group was able to turn into the tension for making knowledge together. This was represented by right turns, away from the straight path with the group's current conocimiento or desconocimiento. This tool then mapped the multiple ways the perspectives were combining to build rich, context-oriented complexity within the group. This tool made the combining of ideas as the group co-created knowledge explicit, visually representing teacher making sense together by expanding... verses a more linear path that often happened as teachers did not offer or incorporate each other's lenses.

Findings

By entering in a discussion, interpreting and making sense together, we developed a more complex interpretation of what was happening with the focal student in the lesson. In part, she may have been nervous. I and the other teachers had created a disruption and we were doing something very new. Yes, there is a well-documented struggle for children to understand the differences of tens and ones. Additionally, maybe the way we represented the tens and ones (with boxes) contributed to the confusion as to what were tens and what were ones and yes, in this center, we saw a student who had a history with hearing problems. This revelation about the hearing aid sparked an ongoing conversation at the school on student files so teachers could get a general report on each student's progress and understand abilities and student backgrounds that might impact teaching. Having overcome the pervasive high-risk nature of the neo-liberal education system in Chile, the teachers were able to address student thinking rich with context, combining student thinking, abilities, with research. The lessons learned in watching this focal student relied on open communication that was not initially happening. When they embraced the tension they paved the way for a more nuanced understanding among the group. That nuance resided in each person's privately held perspective of what was happening with that student, waiting to be held against the other perspectives. In this way we saw the collaborative making of new knowledge between the teachers, the research, through close observation of the student, and background knowledge of the classroom aid.

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